

MusCical Adventures: Virtual Reality as a Musical Training Program

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ABSTRACT

Training programs for improving abilities in speech for CI users are vastly common. However, musical training programs (MTP) for improving music perception is still limited, resulting in CI users having difficulties perceiving, and thereby enjoying, music. Many CI users describe listening to music as an unfulfilling experience, especially when it comes to recognizing melodies and identifying various musical instruments, among other aspects. Additionally, determining the direction of sound is another difficulty CI users often tend to have. Although MTPs have been made utilizing tablet based games, DVD-formats etc., using virtual reality environments for training various aspects of music recognition has not yet been explored. This applies for using VR for spatial sound recognition as well. In this paper, a VR prototype functioning as a MTP with gamification elements will be introduced, with the purpose of improving various musical perception abilities for CI users.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cochlear implants (CI) are advanced systems used for individuals with complete or severe hearing loss to regain functional hearing by stimulating the auditory nerve with electric current [1]. CI users can expect to recover recognition of speech and the ability to differentiate sounds, however, the degree of recovery differs and requires training [2]. Since current rehabilitation training post implantation mainly focuses on training speech and awareness of environmental sounds [3], music perception has not yet been explored to the same degree. Therefore, focusing on improving the listening abilities in regards to both musical perception and sound localization for CI users could be beneficial in gaining a more pleasant music listening experience.

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2. MUSICAL PERCEPTION AND MUSIC TRAINING PROGRAMS FOR CI USERS

Many studies have shown CI users can recognize rhythm on a comparable level as normal hearing (NH) individuals [4] [5]. However, when it comes to identifying melodies, CI users generally tend to have more difficulties compared to NH listeners [5].

Previous research in music training has included timbre recognition [6], identification of musical instruments [7], pitch perception [8] and melodic contour identification (MCI) [5], where CI users abilities in these musical perception aspects improved over time. However, [9] argues the pleasantness of listening to music only increased after focused training for a longer period of time [9].

3. PITCH, TIMBRE AND SPATIAL LOCALIZATION WITH CI

CI users have difficulties perceiving some of the primary elements of music, including pitch and timbre [10], which is essential when identifying musical instruments and melodies. For the majority of CI users the perception of pitch is disrupted caused by the implant itself being out-of-tune [10]. As a result of this disrupt perception of pitch, CI users are only able to correctly identify approximately 19% of melodies [4]. Timbre perception in regards to recognizing musical instruments seems to be notably more difficult for CI users compared to NH individuals [11]. However, more percussive instruments with a faster attack appear to be easier recognizable for CI users [11]. Evidence points to increased music enjoyment when the processing of timbre becomes less demanding [10], indicating training to be able to increase enjoyability.

Unilateral CI users report having difficulties with localization of sounds [12], since it requires perceiving differences in arrival time, frequency and intensity [13]. Research suggests NH individuals to perform 3 times better than bilateral CI users in sound localisation tasks when in VR [13]. Although bilateral CI users have less difficulties with localisation of sounds compared to unilateral users [12], they still have issues with fusing sounds from both ears [14]. Research indicates sound localisation can be improved through training with audio-visual tasks [14]

